

MEASUREMENT OF SWELLING AND ELECTROKINETIC POTENTIAL OF FIBRIN AT VARIOUS HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATIONS.

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The swelling and electrokinetic potential of fibrin have been measured in dilute solutions of a number of mono and polybasic acids. Except in the case of nitric and hydrochloric acids, no parallelism between swelling and electrokinetic potential was observed.

It is well known that proteins like gelatin, fibrin etc, swell in contact with water and dilute solutions of acids and alkalis. The swelling of protein has been found to be minimum at its iso-electric point and as the p_H of the solution in contact with it increases above or decreases below the iso-electric point, the swelling in each case increases, reaches a maximum and then diminishes again. The theories which have been advanced to account for the swelling of proteins distinguish between two types of swelling : (i) at the iso-electric point and (ii) swelling at hydrogen ion concentrations other than that of the iso-electric point.

The swelling at the iso-electric point is usually attributed to the hydration of the protein micelles. Kat (*Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1918, 9, 1) measured the heat evolved and the contraction in volume of the gelatin-water system during the swelling of gelatin and emphasised on the close analogy between this process and the dilution of a strong solution of sulphuric acid with water.

According to Lloyd and Moran (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, A, 147, 342) the water which is imbibed by iso-electric gelatin is held partly as 'firmly bound' water and partly as 'loosely bound' water. The portion of water which can be squeezed out from the gel at a pressure of 8000 lbs per sq. inch is 'loosely bound' water and the other part which begins to be squeezed out at a pressure of 30,000 lbs per sq. inch of the gel is termed 'firmly bound' water. The swelling of gelatin at hydrogen ion concentrations other than that of the iso-electric point has been attributed by Procter and Wilson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 307) and also by Ghosh (*ibid.*, 1928, 711) to the higher concentration of the diffusible ions inside the gel than in the outside solution as a result of Donnan equilibrium.

Tolman and Stern (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **40**, 264) measured the swelling of fibrin in dilute solutions of acids and concluded that there must be a close relationship between the swelling and the electrical charge of fibrin micelles. They suggested that as the electrical charge of the protein micelles increases, the force of repulsion between them also increases and this causes increase in swelling. It may be pointed out that the increase in the electrical charge of the protein micelles may increase their hydration as suggested by Pauli (*Biochem. Z.*, 1909, **18**, 368) and this may also be responsible for the observed increase in swelling in dilute acid or alkaline solutions. A simultaneous measurement of swelling and electrokinetic potential of fibrin was therefore undertaken to ascertain if there exists any relation between the swelling and electrical charge of this protein. The results obtained are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

About 100 g. of fibrin (Merck's) were taken in a beaker containing a normal solution of hydrochloric acid and stirred with a glass rod. After 2 hours the supernatant solution was poured off, a fresh solution of normal hydrochloric acid was added, the mixture stirred and after allowing to stand for about two hours, the supernatant solution was again decanted off. This process was repeated about four times. The swollen mass of fibrin was then repeatedly washed with distilled water until the p_H of the wash liquid was nearly the same as that of the distilled water used. The fibrin was then dried under a small electric fan and finely powdered. The sample thus prepared was used in all our experiments.

The swelling was thus measured by placing the fibrin sample (1 g.) in a tall graduated cylinder and covering the mass with 100 c.c. of the dilute acid solution of the requisite conductivity. The acid solution was cooled to 10° before use. The cylinder was placed inside a refrigerator maintained at 10°. The contents of the cylinder were stirred twice at intervals of three to four hours to ensure uniformity of concentration of hydrogen ions throughout the solution. The volume occupied by the given weight of the fibrin after 24 hours was read from the graduations in the cylinder.

The electrokinetic potential was measured by means of an arrangement used by Mukherjee and co-workers (*Nature*, 1922, **110**, 732) and described in detail in a paper by Ghosh and Roy (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16** 634). The fibrin was transferred from the cylinder to the U-tube and made to occupy its lower part by pressing with a glass rod having a flattened end.

upper part of the U-tube and the connecting tubes were filled with an acid solution having the same conductivity as that of the supernatant liquid. The electro-osmotic velocity U is connected with the electrokinetic potential E by the equation

$$U = \frac{EiD}{4\pi\eta K} \quad \dots (i)$$

where i is the current, K , the specific conductivity of the liquid filling the pores of the diaphragm and D , the dielectric constant and η , the coefficient of viscosity of the solution. For dilute solutions D and η may be assumed to remain constant. Hence the equation (i) can be expressed in the form

$$\frac{U \times K}{i} = E \times c$$

where $c = \frac{D}{4\pi\eta}$ and is a constant for dilute solutions.

Therefore, the electrokinetic potential is proportional to $U \times K$. In the following tables U is expressed in cubic centimetres of water flowing through the diaphragm per second, i , the current in amperes and K , the specific conductivity in reciprocal ohms. The results obtained with mono-basic acids are recorded in Table I and those with polybasic acids in Table II.

TABLE I.

Acid.	Sp. conductivity.	Swelling.	Current.	Charge.	$U \times 10^4$.	$\frac{U \times K}{i}$
Hydrochloric	2.35×10^{-3}	8 c.c.	6 m.amp.	Positive	1.34	5.5×10^{-4}
	1.27×10^{-3}	7	12	"	1.46	1.55
	6.9×10^{-4}	6	7	"	1.16	1.15
	4.1×10^{-4}	5	7	"	1.82	1.07
Nitric	5×10^{-3}	7	10	Positive	0.37	1.85
	2.4×10^{-3}	8	10	"	0.85	2.08
	1.02×10^{-3}	5	8	"	1.46	1.86
	5.8×10^{-4}	5	8	"	1.22	0.8
Trichloro-acetic	3×10^{-4}	4.5	6	"	0.97	0.48
	7×10^{-3}	3	15	Positive	0.24	1.12
	3.2×10^{-3}	4.5	15	"	0.49	1.06
	1.8×10^{-3}	5.5	15	"	0.73	0.88

TABLE II.

Acid.	Sp. conductivity.	Swelling.	Current.	Charge.	$U \times 10^4$.	$U \times K$
Sulphuric	7.3×10^{-3}	6 c.c.	15 m.amp.	Positive	2.9	1.39×10^{-4}
	1.5×10^{-3}	8	15	"	1.46	1.46
	1.2×10^{-3}	6	11	"	1.46	1.59
	7×10^{-4}	6	10	"	1.46	1.02
Sulphosalicylic	7.4×10^{-3}	9.	12	Positive	0.37	2.3
	2.7×10^{-3}	9	8.5	"	0.73	2.3
	1.7×10^{-3}	10	8	"	2.2	4.76
	1.1×10^{-3}	11	8	"	2	2.75
Oxalic	5.5×10^{-3}	11	14	Positive	0.24	0.935
	2.9×10^{-3}	11	12	"	0.73	1.74
	1.5×10^{-3}	12	10	"	0.37	0.55
	1×10^{-3}	12	10	"	0.49	0.49
Succinic	1×10^{-3}	12 c.c.	9	Positive	0.73 c.c.	0.73
	4.9×10^{-4}	13	10	"	0.49	0.27
	3×10^{-4}	10	10	"	0.37	0.11
	2.3×10^{-4}	10	8	"	0.37	0.106
Phosphoric	5.9×10^{-3}	16	10.5	Positive	0.85	4.84
	3.5×10^{-3}	17.5	10	"	1.34	4.55
	2.2×10^{-3}	17.5	8	"	1.34	3.74
	1.4×10^{-3}	17	8	"	1.8	3.08
	1.1×10^{-3}	16	8	"	1.93	2.64
	8.5×10^{-4}	13	6	"	1.82	2.6

DISCUSSION.

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table I that in the case of the two acids, the hydrochloric and the nitric, as their concentration in solution increases, the swelling of fibrin at first increases, reaches a maximum and then diminishes again. The electrokinetic potential of fibrin also changes in the same way as the swelling, the maximum of swelling occurring at the maximum value of the electrokinetic potential. In the case of trichloroacetic acid, however, with the increasing concentration of

the acid, the electrokinetic potential increases while the swelling decreases. This results leads one to doubt if there is any relation between the swelling and the electrokinetic potential of fibrin.

Again, when the results recorded in Table II are examined, it is noticed that in the case of all the polybasic acids used, the maximum of swelling does not occur all at the same concentration of the solution at which the electrokinetic potential is the maximum. In contact with the solutions of sulphosalicylic acid the swelling decreases as the concentration of the acid increases, while the electrokinetic potential at first increases, reaches a maximum, and then decreases. In the case of succinic and phosphoric acids, as the concentration of their solutions increases the the swelling increases, reaches a maximum and then diminishes again, while the electrokinetic potential continues to increase steadily. It appears from these results that there is no relation between the swelling and the electrokinetic potential of fibrin in contact with solutions of dibasic acids used.

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